

Cold sintering of quartz ceramics and their peculiar effective properties

Vojtěch Nečina^{*}, Willi Pabst

Department of Glass and Ceramics, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Cold sintering
Low-temperature densification
Quartz
Silica
Thermal conductivity

ABSTRACT

In the present paper, we demonstrate a densification of quartz by cold sintering and investigate the effect of various parameters (temperature, pressure, dwell time and content of the liquid phase) on the final density. Thermal conductivity and shear modulus are determined based on the measurement of thermal diffusivity and transversal sound velocity, respectively. The measured values are very low compared to existing predictions, thus suggesting a presence of microcracks/pores at grain boundaries. In some cases, a weak temperature dependence of thermal conductivity was observed and points to a presence of amorphous phase and/or crystallographic defects.

1. Introduction

Quartz is one of the most abundant substances in the Earth's crust and a well-studied material, with applications ranging from routine areas like geoenvironment, construction, metallurgy, ceramic and glass industry and thermal energy storage to more specialized fields of use such as pressure sensors, oscillators and various optical elements in its monocristalline form. Some of the latter applications are based on its advantageous piezoelectric, optical and thermal properties [1].

In its various applications, quartz is used either as a loose particles (sand), single crystals or in the form of natural rocks like sandstone or less frequently quartzite. This is mainly because under normal sintering conditions, the preparation of dense polycrystalline quartz is practically impossible due to the well-known low-quartz to high-quartz transition at 573 °C which is accompanied by significant volume contraction due to density difference of 2.65 (low-quartz) and 2.53 g/cm³ (high-quartz) which would result in cracking. Moreover, with even higher temperature high-quartz transforms to other forms of crystalline silica, either directly to cristobalite (high-cristobalite) at temperatures higher than ~1040 °C or first to tridymite (high-tridymite) above 870 °C and then to cristobalite (high-cristobalite) above 1470 °C, respectively [2].

The densification of quartz is therefore limited to hydrothermal processes which were extensively studied in the past and will be discussed in the following section. Very similar to hydrothermal methods is cold sintering (CS), which takes advantage of the pressure-driven dissolution and precipitation of material facilitated by transient liquid phase [3,4].

The main objective of this study was to investigate the feasibility of

CS for the preparation of dense quartz ceramics and to compare their effective thermal conductivity and shear modulus with model predictions while accounting for porosity and microstructure.

2. State of the art

The present section gives a concise overview regarding the pressure solution (densification) of quartz (sand) which was intensively studied in past (starting in the 1960s) as a model material to better understand the geological formation (lithification) of sandstone and other sedimentary rocks. It should be noted that most of these experiments were performed for rather short durations (from days up to months) in comparison to the real conditions of lithification which takes thousands to millions of years [5]. To compensate this immense order-of-magnitude time difference, authors frequently used higher temperatures and more aggressive liquid phases (e.g., NaOH solution), due to the poor solubility of quartz in water which increases only slightly with pressure and temperature (from tens to hundreds of ppm) [6,7].

It is widely accepted that during pressure solution a very thin liquid film of quasi-solid properties is formed between individual grains [8,9]. These properties reveal themselves by the loss of viscous behavior and slower evaporation kinetics [10], both of which have direct impact on pressure solution in CS. Interestingly, it has been suggested that such a quasi-solid film can facilitate the dissolution and diffusion of matter to the free surface of pores, where precipitation takes place [8,11,12]. An alternative theory suggests the presence of so-called island-channel structure between grains, through which the liquid facilitates matter transport [13,14]. In fact, rough surfaces resembling the proposed

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: necinav@vscht.cz (V. Nečina).

island-channel structure at grain contacts were observed in several instances [15–17]. Note, however, that these observations are usually limited to contacts of large quartz grains ($\geq 125 \mu\text{m}$) with polished quartz plate. The island-channel structure could be the result of micro-cracking of the grains, thus creating multiple contacts at which boundaries with thin liquid films are established.

Renton et al. [18] were among the first who studied the pressure solution of quartz and more importantly, the first to underpin their findings by detailed microscopic observations. The authors observed a very limited formation of pits on the surface of a quartz crystal plate in distilled water (marking dissolution of quartz at the point of contact), but substantially larger pits were observed in aqueous NaOH, Na_2CO_3 and NaCl (brine) solutions, which is explained by the higher solubility of quartz in the presence of sodium ions (which is not unexpected because it is similar to the formation of so-called water glass, i.e., non-stoichiometric compounds of SiO_2 and Na_2O). Most importantly, they have observed rims at the edges of contact with grains, thus hinting that the precipitation (overgrowths) of dissolved matter did take place in its vicinity (in the region of low pressure). Note that the pressure was no more than 90 MPa, the temperature was up to 560 °C and the experiments took weeks (up to 48 days) to complete. These observations were later confirmed by de Boer et al. [19] in the case of even longer experiments (up to 255 days), but at lower temperature (330 °C), who also noted the amorphous nature of such precipitates.

Valuable results were published by Rutter [8], who constructed the deformation map of quartz extended by a region of pressure solution. Although these maps are approximative, they do reflect that only at relatively high temperature (~ 650 °C), i.e., above the quartz transition, the deformation mechanism of quartz changes from pressure solution to solid-state diffusion creep (Nabarro-Herring).

The kinetics of pressure solution are governed by either dissolution, diffusion or precipitation. All of them, dissolution [12,16,20,21], diffusion [22] and precipitation [23], have been determined by different researchers as potentially rate-controlling steps (under different conditions). As was highlighted by Niemeijer [20] the rate-controlling step depends on the liquid phase chemistry (presence of ions) that can significantly change solubility. Possibly this could be the reason why Gratier & Guiguet [22] marked diffusion as the rate-controlling step, due to the use of NaOH solution which dramatically increases dissolution rate in comparison to distilled water. Based on the dissolution-diffusion-precipitation model, He et al. [24] concluded that with decreasing grain size the rate-controlling step changes from diffusion to dissolution.

Regarding CS, there is only one publication [25] concerning the preparation of dense polycrystalline quartz by this method. The authors used H_2SiO_3 as a precursor to prepare either a glass (≤ 200 °C) or a polycrystalline ceramic material (> 200 °C) and investigated the effect of NaOH concentration, pressure, temperature and dwell time. Notably the authors observed a plateau in densification at concentrations ≥ 5 M and pressure of ≥ 300 MPa, while increasing temperature and dwell time progressively increased final density.

As a final note, the phenomena observed in quartz pressure solution experiments should be interpreted with caution when applied in the context of CS. The key difference is that pressure solution experiments are performed in a closed system, whereas CS represents a process in a semi-closed system from which the liquid can (and should) evaporate.

3. Material and methods

The samples were prepared by mixing 1.2 g of quartz powder (Sinoenergy, China) with 2 M NaOH (Penta, Czech Republic) solution with pestle and mortar for a short time (~ 1 min) and transferred into a stainless-steel pressing die with inner diameter of 12.7 mm enclosed by heating jacket (MSE Supplies, USA). Each sample was separated from the upper and lower punch by a graphite foil. The cold sintering process was performed by heating up to the maximum temperature at a heating

rate of ~ 10 °C/min. The pressure was applied at room temperature and maintained at the maximum value until the end of the dwell time, then steadily released at ~ 50 °C.

The default processing parameters were set to a temperature of 300 °C, a pressure of 400 MPa, a dwell time of 60 min and 20 vol. % of liquid phase. For subsequent samples, only one processing parameter was varied (200–400 °C, 300–500 MPa, 10–360 min, 0–30 vol. %), while the remaining parameters were kept at their default value.

After preparation, the samples were ground to remove residues of graphite foil and characterized by Archimedes method to determine their bulk density and porosity assuming theoretical density of 2.65 g/cm³.

Microstructure of prepared samples was investigated by scanning electron microscope (SEM) Lyra 3 (Tescan, Czech Republic).

The phase composition of the original powder and the samples (powder compacts) was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a X'Pert diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, Netherlands), equipped with a conventional X-ray tube (CuK α radiation $\lambda = 0.154$ nm, 40 kV, 30 mA, line focus) with a PIXcel detector and standard Bragg-Brentano optics. The samples were measured with 0.04 rad Soller slits, 0.5° divergence slit and 10 mm mask. X-ray patterns were collected in the range of 10° to 90° 2 θ with the step of 0.0131° and a total exposure time of 100 s per frame. Semi-qualitative analysis was performed with the HighScorePlus software package (Malvern PANalytical, Netherlands, version 5.2.0) and PDF-5+ database. Additionally, the purity of powder was checked by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) ARL Perform'X (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Switzerland).

The particle size distribution of the original powder was measured by laser diffraction on a LA-960 particle size analyzer (Horiba, Japan) using strong ultrasonication for particle separation.

The thermal diffusivity at room temperature and up to 500 °C was measured by the laser flash method on LFA 1000 (Linseis, Germany). For this purpose, the samples were coated with graphite on both sides.

The thermal conductivity k was calculated according to Fourier's law

$$k = \alpha \cdot \rho \cdot c_p, \quad (1)$$

where α is thermal diffusivity, ρ bulk density and c_p specific heat capacity. The values of c_p were calculated according to [26]. For all samples (with the exception of samples S2, S3 and S14 that either disintegrated or radially cracked, thus impeding their measurement) the thermal diffusivity was measured at room temperature. Moreover, thermal diffusivity was measured for selected samples (with sufficient differences in porosity) up to 500 °C to investigate the high-temperature behavior of these cold-sintered polycrystalline quartz ceramics.

Shear modulus G was calculated from the transversal sound velocity v_L using the relation

$$v_L = \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}}. \quad (2)$$

The v_L was measured by the ultrasonic wave propagation pulse-echo technique using an advanced thickness gauge 38DL Plus (Olympus, Japan) with a transverse wave probe V156-RM (5 MHz, diameter 5 mm).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Particle size and phase purity

The purity and particle size median declared by the manufacturer were 99 % and 5 μm , respectively, which is in a good agreement with our analysis (see Table 1 and Fig. S1 in the Supplementary materials). It is assumed that Al (the main impurity) is present in the form of aluminosilicates, but XRD did not reveal the presence of any secondary phase in the original powder (see Fig. S2 in Supplementary materials). The original powder consisted of angular particles as displayed in Fig. 1.

XRD of the prepared samples did not reveal the presence of any

Table 1

Impurity concentrations in the starting SiO₂ powder related to Si (excluding O) rounded to tens of ppm.

Element	Na	Mg	Al	Cl	K	Ca	Ti	Fe
Concentration [ppm (at.)]	320	110	6050	180	510	390	60	350

Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of original quartz powder.

secondary phases either. For illustrative purposes, the XRD diffractogram of sample S1 (for experimental conditions see Table 2) is displayed in Fig. 2. This is in accordance with the results of Kang et al. who observed the crystallization of SiO₂ glass into polycrystalline ceramics during CS from 200 to 300 °C [25], thus the presence of significant concentration of amorphous phase is not expected. This does not mean that the presence of glass phase can be ruled out completely. In fact, 20 vol. % of 2 M NaOH solution could yield 1.1–2.6 wt. % if we assume formation of amorphous phase with Na₂O:SiO₂ ratio 1:1–1:4,

Table 2

Bulk density and porosity of SiO₂ samples prepared by CS with varying parameters (temperature, pressure, dwell time and liquid phase content).

Sample	Temp. [°C]	Pressure [MPa]	Dwell time [min]	L. p. content [vol. %]	Total por. [%]	Open por. [%]
S1	300	400	60	20	7.0	5.6
S2	200	400	60	20	18.4	17.5
S3	250				10.6	9.0
S4	350				6.7	5.8
S5	400				8.4	7.1
S6	300	300	60	20	8.9	8.1
S7		350			7.7	6.5
S8		450			6.0	5.2
S9		500			5.5	4.5
S10	300	400	10	20	8.4	8.2
S11			30		9.7	8.6
S12			120		7.8	6.7
S13			360		6.5	5.5
S14	300	400	60	0	^a	^a
S15				5	15.7	14.2
S16				10	8.1	7.1
S17				30	6.6	5.9

a – sample disintegrated.

respectively. This concentration is close to the detection limit for amorphous phase in XRD. Additionally, this amorphous phase could have dissolved during Archimedes measurement.

4.2. Bulk density and porosity

Values of total and open porosity (the former calculated from the bulk density, assuming a theoretical density of 2.65 g/cm³) of the prepared samples are shown in Table 2 and also graphically in Fig. 3a–d. One can notice that temperature has a significant effect on the resulting porosity (Fig. 3a). The lowest temperature resulted in only little densification. Further reduction in porosity was achieved with increasing temperature, but only up to 350 °C, whereas at the maximum temperature of 400 °C a small increase in porosity was observed. A possible explanation could be the faster evaporation of the liquid phase at 400 °C, thus interrupting the densification prematurely.

Concerning the effect of pressure (Fig. 3b), the porosity decreases almost linearly in the tested range 300–500 MPa. If this dependence would be linear in the whole pressure range, it would follow by extrapolation that a pressure of ~800 MPa would be necessary for complete densification. However, the linearity is highly unrealistic due to the effects connected with changes in pore morphology and the curvature seems to be slightly upward curved. If we take a slightly more realistic view and assume a linear relationship with natural logarithm of pressure instead, we can calculate that complete densification requires a pressure of ~1100 MPa. This value exceeds the capability of our equipment and was therefore not tested.

The effect of dwell time (Fig. 3c) seems to be ambiguous. The overall trend suggests that with increasing dwell time, the porosity decreases. However, values at short dwell times (<60 min) deviate from the expected range. This could have been caused by fluctuations in pressure, since the pressure drops due to densification and needs to be compensated manually in our equipment. To address this issue, additional samples were prepared (shown as crosses in Fig. 3c) with strict control of the pressure. Their values fit better into the expected trend, but need to be treated carefully in the context of original samples, since these new samples were prepared later, thus we cannot rule out changes in liquid phase evaporation kinetics due to wear of the die (changes in the clearance). For this reason, these samples are not considered further in the manuscript.

Last but not least, the content of liquid phase had a significant effect on the densification (Fig. 3d). Obviously, without any liquid phase, the densification (except for particle rearrangement and fragmentation) did not happen at all. In fact, the sample (S14) crumbled into several pieces upon ejection from the die and disintegrated when submerged in water for Archimedes measurement. By contrast, even a relatively small content of liquid phase 5 vol. % resulted in a significant reduction in porosity to 15.7 % and doubling the amount to 10 vol. % decreased the porosity even more down to 8.1 %. However, increasing the content up to 20 or 30 vol. % resulted only in a small additional improvement (porosity decreased to 7.0 or 6.6 %, respectively).

This corresponds to the idea that when the content of the liquid phase is low, it first concentrates at the particle contacts (Fig. 4a), due to the action of capillary forces, but the coverage is not perfect and some contacts can be left dry. Further addition of liquid phase increases the homogeneity in the liquid phase distribution, thus saturating completely the interparticle regions (Fig. 4b) and only after that the liquid phase starts to fill the pore space (Fig. 4c), ultimately leading to complete saturation (Fig. 4d), at which point the solid particles start to lose their cohesion by capillary forces and enter a quasi-suspension state. From the viewpoint of the main driving mechanism during CS – pressure solution – it is essential for the liquid phase to be present at the particle contacts [8,9,11]. All the liquid phase in the rest of the pore space is actually redundant for the CS process and serves only as a reservoir compensating its evaporation.

It should be noted that each system (i.e., each combination of solid

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of sample S1 with marked reflexes of low-quartz.

Fig. 3. a–d: Total porosity of SiO₂ samples prepared by CS versus temperature (a), pressure (b), dwell time (c) and content of the liquid phase (d); the default processing parameters were 300 °C, 400 MPa, 60 min and 20 vol. %; additional values (crosses) in (c) correspond to second batch of samples.

and liquid phase) will have different thresholds for the content of the liquid phase depending on the surface tension, wettability, particle size and morphology of the particles. For example, it is expected that with decreasing particle size (increasing surface area), the system will require larger volume of liquid phase in comparison to a coarser powder.

Interestingly, the majority of samples prepared within this work were split into two or three disc-shaped pieces, with a few exceptions of samples prepared at either high temperature (400 °C) or with either a low or a high content of liquid phase (5 and 30 vol. %). This could have been a result of pressure build-up [27] or simply a problem connected with the ejection of the sample that randomly resulted in cracking. Another interesting observation was condensed water on the aluminum cap during ejection of the samples. This was observed only for samples prepared at low temperature (≤ 250 °C). This means that even at such a relatively high temperature kept for 60 min (in the context of water thermodynamics), the system still contained enough liquid phase for densification.

4.3. Microstructural investigation

The microstructure investigation revealed indented grain contacts (pressure solution contacts as described by de Boer et al. [19]) visible on large grains as shown in Fig. 5a. This indicates the operation of the pressure solution mechanism. One could argue that these indents could also be due to plastic deformation. However, based on the literature, quartz does not experience plastic deformation below 550 °C [8,28]. Although the presence of water (hydroxyl groups) generally decreases the temperature required for the plastic deformation of quartz [29], it would have to be incorporated in the quartz structure itself, and the diffusion of water in quartz is negligible at the temperatures tested within this study (≤ 400 °C). Similar conclusions were drawn by Nie-meijer et al. [20], who investigated the compaction of quartz sand at 400–600 °C and ruled out plastic deformation (dislocation creep) as the main driving force of densification.

In multiple instances, finely structured grain boundaries were

Fig. 4. a–d: Schematic representation of the gradual filling of the pore space between spherical particles by increasing the content of liquid phase.

observed, as can be seen in Fig. 5b–c. These could represent the aforementioned island-channel structure reported previously in the literature [15–17]. However, in contrast to these previous reports, the present grain boundaries are indeed very finely structured, presumably due to much smaller grain size.

Moreover, serious fragmentation was frequently observed in all samples. An example can be seen in Fig. 5d. While the original powder was composed of fine particles (0.2–1 μm) as well, their volume concentration was below 3 vol. % (see Fig S1), which is far less than the observed quantity during our SEM investigation.

4.4. Effective properties

The thermal conductivity and shear modulus of samples at room temperature (20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) are listed in Table 3. Despite the relatively high density of the samples, both properties exhibit extremely low values. To put it into perspective, the absolute thermal conductivity and shear modulus of completely dense polycrystalline low-quartz with randomly oriented grains should be 7.9 W/(m·K) and 41.1 GPa, respectively [30, 31].

It was previously reported [19] that pressure solution can result in the precipitation of an amorphous phase, which could explain the low values of both properties. However, even when assuming the highest possible content of amorphous phase (see Supplementary materials) and following the lower Wiener bound and the lower Paul bound (also called Reuss bound), which provides the lowest possible value for the effective thermal conductivity and shear modulus of a two-phase mixture, the

Fig. 5. a–d: Fracture surface of sample S1 with visible indented grain contacts created by smaller grains (a), fracture surface of sample S9 with notable wrinkled appearance of the grain boundary (b), possible remains of island-channel structure (c) and result of fragmentation in a form of very fine grains (d).

Table 3

Total porosity, thermal conductivity and shear modulus at room temperature (20 °C) of samples prepared by CS.

Sample	Total por. [%]	Thermal conductivity [W/(m·K)]	Shear modulus [GPa]
S1	7.0	2.02	9.9
S2	18.4	^b	^b
S3	10.6	^b	^b
S4	6.7	1.14	^c
S5	8.4	2.16	11.5
S6	8.9	1.30	5.2
S7	7.7	1.45	6.2
S8	6.0	1.36	10.2
S9	5.5	1.78	12.3
S10	8.4	1.56	5.2
S11	9.7	1.68	7.9
S12	7.8	1.41	5.9
S13	6.5	1.34	5.1
S14	^a	^a	^a
S15	15.7	0.98	^c
S16	8.1	1.29	4.7
S17	6.6	1.66	7.5

a – Sample disintegrated.

b – Sample was radially fractured.

c – Sample could not be measured.

thermal conductivity and shear modulus of the dense solid phase will be reduced to 5.4–7.5 W/(m·K) and 39.9–40.9 GPa, respectively (when the properties of amorphous silica are assumed to be 1.35 W/(m·K) and 30.6 GPa [31,32]). So, the relative effective properties are still dramatically below even the lowest analytical predictions for convex pores, which are given by the Pabst-Gregorová-type exponential relations [33] as displayed in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. In both graphs, the values of effective properties are calculated for the two extreme cases assuming either pure quartz or quartz with a maximum content of amorphous phase (see Supplementary materials). This means that for each individual sample, the true relative thermal conductivity lies between the two displayed values.

The fact that even with these two extreme assumptions for calculating the properties of the dense solid the relative property values are not too far apart, suggests that the primary cause of the low values is related to porosity and not to the phase composition. In fact, the pore morphology can reduce effective properties dramatically, especially

when such pores are located at the grain boundaries in the form of microcracks or anisometric or concave voids [34,35].

As reported in the literature [12,16,36], pressure solution of quartz leads to microcracking in the early stage of densification (pressure application). In the present study, the pressure was applied at room temperature. Possibly, many of these defects are of nanometric size, thus making their identification by SEM very challenging. The finely structured grain boundaries were observed in some cases (see Fig. 5b–c). Therefore, we assume that present samples are composed of quartz grains, macropores (of the size in the same order of magnitude as the grain size) and nano-sized pores or microcracks in the grain boundary region as schematically displayed in Fig. 8 together with additional microscopic evidence of the grain boundary region with typical wrinkling. In any case, this finding needs further investigation.

Thermal conductivity versus temperature of selected samples is displayed in Fig. 9. As expected, it decreases with increasing temperature. We describe the data by an empirical fit relation in the form of a reciprocal model assuming a linear dependence of the inverse thermal conductivity on temperature which provides good approximation in the high temperature (>300 K) region where the lattice thermal conductivity is dominated by phonon–phonon Umklapp scattering [37]

$$\frac{1}{k} = a + b \cdot T \quad (3)$$

where, a and b are constants. The fits are displayed in Fig. 9. Interestingly, for sample S8, which has almost the same porosity as sample S9, has a significantly lower thermal conductivity and at the same time a less pronounced temperature dependence. These could indicate a higher content of amorphous phase between and/or crystallographic defects (possibly dislocations due to high pressure application) within the grains (crystallites). Both samples (S8 and S9) have a very low porosity, thus suggesting the presence of fine pores at grain boundaries (possibly in a form of the island channel structure) as previously discussed.

Perhaps with the following thoughts we are balancing on the edge of speculation but let us display thermal conductivity versus pressure in Fig. 10. While the porosity of samples decreases over the whole range of pressures, the thermal conductivity increases only up to 400 MPa and then decreases abruptly at 450 MPa and increases again at 500 MPa. At the same time sample S8 prepared at the pressure of 450 MPa, respectively, exhibits a lower sensitivity of thermal conductivity to

Fig. 6. Values of relative thermal conductivity versus porosity of SiO₂ samples prepared by CS in comparison to the exponential prediction.

Fig. 7. Values of relative shear modulus versus porosity of SiO₂ samples prepared by CS in comparison to the exponential prediction.

Fig. 8. Fracture surface (sample S9) with notable wrinkling (left) and schematic representation of microstructure composed of grains, macropores and small pores/microcracks in the grain boundary region (right).

temperature (see Fig. 9).

The positive effect of pressure during pressure solution is threefold: 1) better rearrangement of particles, 2) increase of solubility and 3) particle size refinement due to their fracturing. This can explain why the density increases with increasing pressure. However, there is at least one negative effect that is rarely mentioned in literature: reduction of the liquid film thickness by the so-called process of disjoining [38] which will limit the diffusion [9] and can ultimately lead to the rupture of the liquid film.

In the present case, we suppose that above 400 MPa the samples experience more pronounced microcracking, which would on the one side increase a solubility of quartz due to larger surface area, resulting in better densification, and on the other side create rough grain boundary regions, resulting in the presence of fine pores upon water evaporation. In fact, van Noort et al. proposed a similar mechanism, where they assumed an open-channel (island-channel) structure at the grain boundaries [16]. A more detailed investigation of this issue is beyond the scope of the present article and will be the subject of future work.

5. Conclusions

Samples of polycrystalline quartz ceramics were successfully prepared by cold sintering using a 2 M NaOH solution as the liquid phase. Among the investigated processing parameters (temperature, pressure, dwell time and liquid phase content) it was shown that, except for dwell time, all of them have significant effect on the final density (porosity). It was observed that a temperature of at least 250 °C is necessary for sufficient densification to take place. Similarly, the presence of liquid phase is essential for the activation of the pressure solution mechanism, however, it was observed that very little densification is achieved with ≥ 10 vol. % of liquid phase.

Despite the relatively high density, the effective properties (thermal conductivity and shear modulus) exhibited very low values. As the most plausible explanation, it was concluded that such low values are associated with the presence of microcracks/pores at grain boundaries. In multiple instances, finely structured (wrinkled) grain boundaries were observed, but detailed observation of microcracks/pores at the grain boundary is lacking, possibly due to their extremely small size.

Fig. 9. Thermal conductivity of samples S1, S8, S9, S11, S12 and S15 versus temperature.

Fig. 10. Thermal conductivity of samples prepared by CS at various pressures with values of total porosity (calculated with the density of low-quartz).

Finally, some sample showed a weak temperature dependence of thermal conductivity, indicating a relatively high content of amorphous phase and/or crystallographic defects.

Data availability statement

The original raw data for this paper are available at: 10.5281/zenodo.18244921.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Vojtěch Nečina: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Willi Pabst:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This work has been funded by a grant from the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631, Materials and technologies for sustainable development).

This work is part of the project “New methods for glass phase determination and their application for the effective property prediction of silicate ceramics and refractories” (project GA 25–16482S) funded by the Czech Science Foundation (Grantová agentura České republiky).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.oceram.2026.100946](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2026.100946).

References

- [1] J. Götz, Chemistry, textures and physical properties of quartz — geological interpretation and technical application, *Mineral. Mag.* 73 (4) (2009) 645–671.
- [2] P.J. Heaney, Structure and chemistry of the low-pressure silica polymorphs, Eds. in: P.J. Heaney, C.T. Prewitt, G.V. Gibbs (Eds.), *Silica: Physical Behavior, Geochemistry and Materials Applications*, 1994, pp. 1–40.
- [3] S. Grasso, M. Biesuz, L. Zoli, G. Taveri, A.I. Duff, D. Ke, A. Jiang, M.J. Reece, A review of cold sintering processes, *Adv. Appl. Ceram.* 119 (3) (2020) 115–143.
- [4] A. Galotta, V.M. Sglavo, The cold sintering process: a review on processing features, densification mechanisms and perspectives, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 41 (16) (2021) 1–17.
- [5] W. von Engelhardt, *Sedimentary Petrology Part III: The Origin of Sediments and Sedimentary rocks*, E. Schweizerbart, Stuttgart, 1977.
- [6] D.A. Crerar, G.M. Anderson, Solubility and solvation reactions of quartz in dilute hydrothermal solutions, *Chem. Geol.* 8 (2) (1971) 107–122.
- [7] G.W. Morey, R.O. Fournier, J.J. Rowe, The solubility of quartz in water in the temperature interval from 25° to 300° C, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.* 26 (10) (1962) 1029–1043.
- [8] E.H. Rutter, The kinetics of rock deformation by pressure solution, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A* 283 (1312) (1976) 203–219.
- [9] P.K. Weyl, Pressure solution and the force of crystallization: a phenomenological theory, *J. Geophys. Res.* 64 (11) (1959) 2001–2025.
- [10] J.C. Henniker, The depth of the surface zone of a liquid, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 21 (2) (1949) 322–341.
- [11] E.H. Rutter, Pressure solution in nature, theory and experiment, *J. Geol. Soc.* 140 (5) (1983) 725–740.

- [12] P.M.T.M. Schutjens, Experimental compaction of quartz sand at low effective stress and temperature conditions, *J. Geol. Soc.* 148 (3) (1991) 527–539.
- [13] R. Raj, Creep in polycrystalline aggregates by matter transport through a liquid phase, *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 87 (B6) (1982) 4731–4739.
- [14] C.J. Spiers, P.M.T.M. Schutjens, Densification of crystalline aggregates by fluid-phase diffusional creep, in: D.J. Barber, P.G. Meredith (Eds.), *Deformation Processes in Minerals, Ceramics and Rocks*, Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 1990, pp. 334–353.
- [15] P.M. Schutjens, C.J. Spiers, A.Rik Niemeijer, Surface microstructures developed on polished quartz crystals embedded in wet quartz sand compacted under hydrothermal conditions, *Sci. Rep.* 11 (1) (2021) 14920.
- [16] R. van Noort, C.J. Spiers, G.M. Pennock, Compaction of granular quartz under hydrothermal conditions: controlling mechanisms and grain boundary processes, *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 113 (B12) (2008).
- [17] V. Nečina, Transparent ceramics by cold sintering process – challenges and opportunities, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 45 (13) (2025) 117519.
- [18] J.J. Renton, M.T. Heald, C.B. Cecil, Experimental investigation of pressure solution of quartz, *J. Sediment. Res.* 39 (3) (1969) 1107–1117.
- [19] R.B. de Boer, P.J.C. Nagtegaal, E.M. Duyvis, Pressure solution experiments on quartz sand, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.* 41 (2) (1977) 257–264.
- [20] A. Niemeijer, C.J. Spiers, B. Bos, Compaction creep of quartz sand at 400–600 °C: experimental evidence for dissolution-controlled pressure solution, *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 195 (2002) 261–275.
- [21] T. Dewers, A. Hajash, Rate laws for water-assisted compaction and stress-induced water-rock interaction in sandstones, *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 100 (B7) (1995) 13093–13112.
- [22] J.P. Gratier, R.Guiguet Irigm, Experimental pressure solution-deposition on quartz grains: the crucial effect of the nature of the fluid, *J. Struct. Geol.* 8 (8) (1986) 845–856.
- [23] A.M. Mullis, Determination of the rate-limiting mechanism for quartz pressure dissolution, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.* 57 (7) (1993) 1499–1503.
- [24] W. He, D. Sparks, A. Hajash, Reactive transport at stressed grain contact and creep compaction of quartz sand, *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 118 (2) (2013) 497–510.
- [25] S. Kang, X. Zhao, J. Guo, Y. Xiao, Y. Yang, B. He, X. Wang, L. Yang, R. Liao, Evolution from transparent SiO₂ glass to ceramics enabled by cold sintering with a transient chemistry: h₂SiO₃, *Scr. Mater.* 233 (2023) 115522.
- [26] L. Kotrbová, T. Uhlřřová, W. Pabst, J. Hubáľková, M. Kotouček, Thermal conductivity of silica refractories and its temperature dependence during thermal cycling, compared to silicite and sandstone, *Open Ceram* 21 (2025) 100735.
- [27] A. Jabr, H.N. Jones, A.P. Argüelles, S. Trolrier-McKinstry, C. Randall, R. Bermejo, Scaling up the cold sintering process of ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 43 (12) (2023) 5319–5329.
- [28] R.D. Baěta, K.H.G. Ashbee, Plastic deformation and fracture of quartz at atmospheric pressure, *Philos. Mag.* 15 (137) (1967) 931–938.
- [29] J.D. Blacic, J.M. Christie, Plasticity and hydrolytic weakening of quartz single crystals, *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 89 (B6) (1984) 4223–4239.
- [30] W. Pabst, J. Hostaša, Thermal conductivity of ceramics: from monolithic to multiphase, from dense to porous, from micro to nano, Ed, in: M.C. Wythers (Ed.), *Advances in Materials Science Research*, Nova Science Publishers, Inc., 2012, pp. 1–112.
- [31] W. Pabst, E. Gregorová, Elastic properties of silica polymorphs - a review, *Ceram.-Silik* 57 (2013) 167–184.
- [32] I. Fanderlik, *Silica Glass and Its Application*, Elsevier Science, 2013.
- [33] W. Pabst, E. Gregorová, Critical Assessment 18: elastic and thermal properties of porous materials – rigorous bounds and cross-property relations, *Mater. Sci. Technol.* 31 (15) (2015) 1801–1808.
- [34] W. Pabst, T. Uhlřřová, E. Gregorová, A. Wiegmann, Young’s modulus and thermal conductivity of model materials with convex or concave pores – from analytical predictions to numerical results, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 38 (7) (2018) 2694–2707.
- [35] W. Pabst, T. Uhlřřová, E. Gregorová, A. Wiegmann, Relative Young’s modulus and thermal conductivity of isotropic porous ceramics with randomly oriented spheroidal pores – Model-based relations, cross-property predictions and numerical calculations, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 38 (11) (2018) 4026–4034.
- [36] W. He, A. Hajash, D. Sparks, Evolution of fluid chemistry in quartz compaction systems: experimental investigations and numerical modeling, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.* 71 (20) (2007) 4846–4855.
- [37] G.A. Slack, The thermal conductivity of nonmetallic crystals, Eds, in: H. Ehrenreich, F. Seitz, D. Turnbull (Eds.), *Solid State Physics*, Academic Press, 1979, pp. 1–71.
- [38] J.F. Padday, Cohesive properties of thin films of liquids adhering to a solid surface, *Disc. Faraday Soc.* 1 (0) (1970) 64–74.